

Streamlining RDM Support: Implementing a Ticket System and a Knowledge Base for the bwFDM-Helpdesk

Cora F. Krömer¹

¹Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Germany

*Correspondence: Cora F. Krömer, cora.kroemer@kit.edu

Abstract

The federal state initiative for research data management in Baden-Württemberg (bwFDM) [1] is advancing research data management support on the federal state level by implementing a new helpdesk system that will provide faster, more efficient support for researchers and staff at research institutions in Baden-Württemberg. The bwFDM-helpdesk aims primarily at academics and support staff working at research institutions that do not have any in-house RDM support. Beyond that, the helpdesk is available to RDM support teams at universities seeking federal state-level support with regards to projects that are in line with the goals and objectives of Baden-Württemberg's research data strategy and its implementation concept, which receive organisational support by bwFDM.

The helpdesk's current email-based system for handling enquiries is not scalable and lacks a sustainable knowledge base. As of now, the bwFDM-team discusses all enquiries via a direct messenger platform before sending out e-mail replies. Any information collected for the responses is stored via text documents in the bwFDM cloud. However, this approach is not scalable and the knowledge is not stored in a sustainable or searchable fashion.

To mend these limitations, we are currently integrating a ticket system and knowledge base into our workflow. Both of these elements will enable us to cater to academics and support staff from research institutions in Baden-Württemberg in a more advanced form, allowing us to scale our support and making it more sustainable.

Moreover, we are leveraging the joint support portal [2] for research-related state services in Baden-Württemberg, hosted and technically supported at Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), making use of its centralized helpdesk platform for services like bwSync&Share, bwHPC, and bwCloud. This portal has recently been migrated to the open-source software Zammad, which is also used by the EOSC-helpdesk and several NFDI consortia (e.g., NFDI4Chem, NFDI4Objects, GHGA). As they are based on the same software, it may be possible to connect the different helpdesks via technical interfaces, if this proves to be worthwhile in the future. By utilizing the joint support portal, bwFDM can offer general RDM-related consultations as a state service, which facilitates collaborations with other research-related state services. Along these lines,

tickets can easily be processed in a joint fashion. Furthermore, the system offers an integrated knowledge base that can be built up and utilised by all participating services. Additionally, the portal's connection to bwIDM [3] means that future RDM support personnel at state level, such as data stewards at other research institutions can be involved on a low-threshold basis.

Apart from the technical dimension, we are contributing to RDM support services at federal state and national level by participating in the joint support portal and the Working Group RDM Helpdesk Network [4] in the NFDI section Education & Training, promoting and fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and support across institutions.

Keywords

Helpdesk, General RDM Support, Federal State Initiative, bwFDM

Author contributions

Cora F. Krömer: Conceptualization, Project administration, Writing – original draft, writing – review & editing

Béla Koch: Conceptualization, writing – review & editing

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Funding

bwFDM is funded by the Baden-Württemberg Ministry of Science, Research and Arts.

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